

Implementation of cultivation technology environmentally friendly on pest intensity and chili growth in Lampung

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ABSTRACT

Gisting District is one of the vegetable cultivation centers in Lampung Province. Some dry lands in this area are grown with vegetable commodities including chili. Most of the chili cultivation techniques rely using chemical materials. Initially productivity can increase, but in the longterm period they will endanger the communities in the crop, including natural enemies and humans. This study will compare between chili cultivation using environmentally friendly technology (cultivation and control of pests/diseases) and cultivation with chemical pesticides use (especially maintenance). The results showed that in environmentally friendly chili cultivation the level of pest attack was 20% lower than ordinary cultivation. Plant growth shows the height and width of the canopy is better compared to ordinary cultivation. Likewise with production, environmentally friendly cultivation results in a production that is 20% higher compared to ordinary cultivation.

Keywords: *Chili, environmentally friendly, cultivation*

INTRODUCTION

Chili is one of strategic commodities which control inflation control and price stability in horticultural development (Direktorat Jenderal Hortikultura, 2011). Besides having high economic value, chili (*Capsicum annuum* L.) is also able to adapt to a wide environment. This plant can grow in neither lowland areas nor highland areas with altitude of 1400 m above sea level (asl). The red chilli centers in the lowlands are generally in dry land and rice fields that are planted during dry conditions (Sumarni and Muharam, 2005).

Chili is a typical tropical vegetable because 69-75% of the planting areas is located in an area with a height of 10.00 - 500 m above sea level. In Lampung Province, this commodity has the widest harvest area compared to the area of harvest of other types of vegetables and gets priority to develop. National chili productivity tends to be around 8.47 t/ha, while the productivity in Lampung is only 7.54 t/ha (BPS, 2017; Dirjenhorti, 2017). The yield of red chili potential reached 20 t/ha.

There are many factors that cause the low productivity of red chillies in Lampung, i.e. application of cultivation techniques are not in line with technological innovation, use of chemical materials are relatively high, the influence of climate and farmers' resources are still low. Related to climate change, climatic conditions often is less suitable for the growth and development of red chili. Climate change is a change in the physical condition of the earth's atmosphere, including temperature and rainfall distribution which has a wide impact on various sectors of human life (Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup, 2009). Climate change is expected to have a significant impact on agricultural production in Indonesia, especially food crops. These impacts can be direct, such as decrease of crop productivity, changes in rainfall patterns and intensity of rainfall due to increased air temperature that causes drought and flooding (Boer, 2010). Technological innovations of red chilli cultivation off-are needed to to increase the productivity of chili and shallots so that they can maintain the availability of chili throughout the year so that prices remain controlled.

The lack of farmers knowledge about good cultivation causes a lot of loss of red chillies in crops, especially how to manage pests and plant diseases. Lack of knowledge about the management of plant-disturbing organisms encourages farmers to use pesticides. Pesticides for farmers are generally considered a guarantee of production so that their use tends to be unwise with excessive amounts and types. Farmers believe that pesticide is a more effective way to control pests and diseases and to maintain stabil chili yield. Based on the survey results, there are more than 60 types of pesticides used by farmers in chili production centers. Frequency of pesticide use range from once every 2-3 days per week or about 35-50% of the total production costs. Adiyoga (2007) and Setiawati et al. (2011) reported that in one growing season, farmers used pesticides 21-30 times. The overall use of pesticides in agriculture reaches 15,416 tons, an increase of around 7% per year.

Currently, chili farmers generally control pest only relying on chemical pesticides. This can cause environmental damage, killing of useful organisms, and cause resistance and resurgence in pests. As a result, in the longterm period they will also affect the production of red chili produced. Various innovations in red chili cultivation technology and control of pests and diseases have been produced by Indonesian Vegetables Research Institute that ranging from ecosystem management, balanced fertilization, maintenance to harvest (Setiawati et al., 2005).

In this activity aims to examine the effect of the application of environmentally friendly chili cultivation and ordinary cultivation on chili production in Lampung.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and Time

The study was carried out from April to December 2016, in Tanggamus District, Lampung province. The study covered an area of 1.0 ha.

Assessment design

The design used was "zero-one approach". The technological package introduced was stressed on control of pests with low pesticides use. In detail the technology package introduced is as follows:

In the nursery

1. Nursery covered with chiffon or organdy.
2. The nursery is a bit far from the land affected by the disease.
3. Watering Tiametoxam (Actara) insecticide solution (0.5 ml/l) was carried out at a dose of 50 ml/plant at the age of 2 and 4 weeks after seedling to reduce pest attack on the red chili seedlings in the nursery.

In the field

1. Planting intercepting plants 4 rows of corn around the chili 1.5 months before planting chili aims to reduce the attack of pests.
2. To reduce whitefly populations and other pests, 40-50 pieces/ha of yellow trap are installed. The trap is installed at the time of planting.
3. Perform sanitation on weeds that are hosts for whitefly and other pests/diseases.
4. Eradication of plants infected with viruses.
5. Using plant-based pesticides.

Non IPM packages include: More emphasis on the use of chemical pesticides/in accordance with farmers' habits.

Observation

Data collected included: (1) Plant growth (canopy height and diameter), (2) Population of whitefly, fruit fly, armyworm, aphids, and thrips (tail) caught, (4) Number and intensity of downy mildew/Yellow/curly and withered (in%), (5) Components and production of fruit (kg/gram/plant) include fruit length (cm), weight of 10 chili (g), fruit production (g/plant), and (d) Total production (kg/ha), and (6) Observations made on 5 plants/beds.

Disease intensity

To calculate disease intensity, the formula is used:

$$I = \frac{\sum (n_i \times v_i)}{Z \times N} \times 100 \% \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Description :

I = Attack intensity

n_i = The number of plants observed from each category of attack is the same.

v_i = Scale value of each attack category.

Z = The scale value of the category of attack is highest

N = Number of plants observed

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents that the vegetative growth of chili with environmentally friendly cultivation is better than conventional cultivation or farmers' methods

Table 1. Vegetative observations of chili in two crop cultivation systems in Gisting Permai Village, Tanggamus, Lampung province

Observation	Farmer Cultivation	Environmentally friendly technology
Plant height at harvest (cm)	82.5 a	107.0 b
Canopy width	68.0 a	69.3 a
Number of branches	9.0 a	9.1 a

The number on each line followed by the same letter is not significantly different according to the t test at the 5% level.

Plant height with an environmentally friendly cropping system is significantly higher (107.0 cm) than farmers practices (82.8 cm). Likewise, the width of the canopy component and the number of branches of an environmentally friendly cropping system are better than the way of the farmers, although not significantly different. Environmentally friendly planting systems use more natural resurces such as manure, biofertilizers and other beneficial microorganisms such as Trichoderma, PGPR, corine and cow urine. The use of natural resources causes the chili growth better than more chemicals application. The results showed that the use of several types of solid organic fertilizers could improve all variables of plant growth and yield (Rochman, 2015). The importance of organic fertilizer is to restore the product of land productivity. According to Simanungkalit et al. (2005), one of the efforts to

control soil damage is by reducing the use of synthetic fertilizers and increasing the use of organic fertilizers.

Eco-friendly cultivation is more visible, especially in the control of plant disease pests. Based on observation, the level of pest and disease attacks is relatively lower by using a control system that uses more botanical pesticides and biological control (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of cultivation methods on the presence of major pests in chili.

Treatment	Fruit flies		Thrips		Armyworm
	Population caught in 2 months	Intensity (%)	Population in 3 young leaves	Intensity (%)	Intensity (%)
Farmer cultivation	128.00 a	26.50 a	17.33 a	78.33 a	0.01 a
Environmentally friendly technology	117.67 b	16.33 b	14.33 b	52.33 b	0.01 a

The number on each line followed by the same letter is not significantly different according to the t test at the 5% level.

Table 2 presents that the main pests (fruit fly, thrips and armyworm) in environmentally friendly cultivation is significantly less than farmers practices. This is due to the way farmers who intensively use chemical pesticides to control plant-disturbing organisms affect negatively the pest itself which becomes resistant, the occurrence of pest resistance and the possibility of many natural enemies being killed. According to Hasyim et al. (2015), increasing use of pesticides has a negative impact on the environment, including crop productivity and stimulates the occurrence of regulator capacity degradation (parasitoid/predator and others) in an ecosystem. In addition to resulting in inefficient production and negative impacts on target pests and ecosystems, consumers will not choose products that currently choose a concept called consumer value perception (CVP). Efforts to control environmentally friendly pests by reducing the use of chemical pesticides can increase the availability of natural enemies in nature. The use of pesticides in addition to having a positive impact can also have a negative impact if the use is unwise. The unwise pesticide use can cause resurgence, resistance, death of natural enemies, and environmental pollution through residues left behind and cause poisoning in humans whose long-term impacts are more detrimental than the benefits obtained. Therefore, attention to controlling more environmentally friendly pests is greater for reducing the use of synthetic pesticides.

Table 3 presents that the number of plants attacked by wilt and complex viruses and anthracnose in environmentally friendly cultivation was less than the farming system of farmers.

Table 3. Effect of cultivation methods on the presence of major diseases in chili

Treatment	The number of plants withered up to the age of 55 DAP (%)	The intensity of the disease at the age of 75 DAP	
		curly/virus complex (%)	Antraknosa (%)
Farmer cultivation	16.33 a	78.33 a	26.33 a
Environmentally friendly technology	6.33 b	52.33 b	19.33 b

The number on each line followed by the same letter is not significantly different according to the t test at the 5% level.

In environmentally friendly cultivation, antagonistic microorganisms such as *Trichoderma* are also used. It is known that *Trichoderma* has antagonistic ability against pathogenic fungi. *Trichoderma* is easily found on soil and plant roots. These fungi include beneficial microorganisms, avirulent to host plants, and can parasitize other fungi. *Trichoderma* sp. able to suppress *anthracnose* development between 63.89-91.37%. *T. harzianum* is more effective than *T. koningii* and *T. viride* (Hasyim et.al., 2015).

The use of environmentally friendly cultivation also affects the chili production. From the observations it can be seen that with the use of pesticides 7%, it is quite capable to increase the yield of chillies by around 20% compared to the cultivation of farmers (Table 4).

Table 4. Average use of pesticides, and production components in two ways of cultivating chili.

Treatment	Use of pesticides (%)	Fruit length (cm)	Weight of 100 pieces (g)	Productivity (t/ha)
Farmer cultivation	45	11.5 a	230 a	5.55 a
Environmentally friendly technology	7	14.3 b	365 b	8.18 b

The number on column followed by the same letter is not significantly different according to the t test at the 5% level.

The use of environmentally friendly materials, such as organic fertilizers, botanical pesticides and antagonistic microorganisms provides benefits in increasing plant growth, plant fitness, so that plants are more resistant to pests and diseases. Besides that, the use of natural methods in managing pests causes fewer pests and a source of infection in chili plantations. These advantages cause chili plants to produce well, where production components such as fruit length, 100 fruit yields and chili productivity using higher environmentally friendly cultivation are significantly different compared to farmers' methods (Table 4).

The loss yield caused by the pests and diseases spurred farmers to always carry out plant protection efforts, one of which was the use of pesticides. Pesticides are often used as the main choice because pesticides have high killing power, their use is easy, and the results are fast to know. Farmers commonly anticipate pests from early plant growth. The presence of pests in the land will encourage farmers to use pesticides excessively by increasing the dose, frequency of spraying and the composition of the type of pesticide mixture used. Not even a few farmers adhere to a blanket system cover where there is or no pest, the pesticide is still applied. The use of pesticides greatly affects human health and the environment. According to estimates by the World Health Organization (WHO) and Programs Environment of the United Nations (UNEP), 1-5 million cases of pesticide poisoning occur in workers who work in the agricultural sector (Mourad, 2005).

CONCLUSIONS

Environmentally friendly chili cultivation can reduce pest attack 20% higher than than ordinary cultivation. Plant growth parameters (plant height, canopy width) in environmentally friendly cultivation is better compared to ordinary cultivation. Likewise with production, environmentally friendly cultivation results in a production that is 20% higher compared to ordinary cultivation.

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